

Supplemental File to “Task-Aware Dynamic Transformer for Efficient Arbitrary-Scale Image Super-Resolution”

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1 Content

In this supplementary file, we further elaborate our Task-Aware Dynamic Transformer (TADT) as an efficient feature extractor for Arbitrary-Scale Image Super-Resolution. Specifically, we present

- more ablation studies of our TADT in §2;
- more quantitative results of our TADT in §3;
- more visual comparisons of our TADT and other feature extractors on natural image ASSR in §4.

2 Ablation Studies

Here, we perform more ablation studies to investigate the working mechanism of our TADT feature extractor on image ASSR. Similar to the main paper, all ablation experiments here are conducted on our TADT integrated with the arbitrary-scale upsampler LIIF [2].

1) Effectiveness of using binary mask M in our intensity loss $\mathcal{L}_\beta$. To illustrate this point, we remove the binary mask M in $\mathcal{L}_\beta$ and directly set $\mathcal{L}_\beta = \beta$ in the loss function $\mathcal{L}$ to train our TADT. We visualize the β with different s in our TADT when $\mathcal{L}_\beta = \beta$ by the red curve in Figure 1. One can see that, the β value in our TADT goes a slight ascent and then sweep down to about 0.1, which is unreasonable. Quantitative results reported in Table 1 further demonstrate that excluding the mask M from the intensity loss $\mathcal{L}_\beta$ leads to a significant performance drop, with a decrease of 0.09 dB for $\times 8$ upsampling. This validates the effectiveness of using a binary mask M in our intensity loss $\mathcal{L}_\beta$ to train our TADT for image ASSR.

Table 1. PSNR (dB) results of our TADT trained with $\mathcal{L}_\beta$ using the binary mask or not on Urban100 [5].

$\mathcal{L}_\beta$	In-scale			Out-of-scale	
	$\times 2$	$\times 3$	$\times 4$	$\times 6$	$\times 8$
$\mathcal{L}_\beta = \beta$	33.66	29.56	27.36	24.73	23.18
$\mathcal{L}_\beta = \beta M$	33.65	29.58	27.37	24.75	23.27

Figure 1. The predicted β in our TADT *w.r.t.* different SR scales s .

Table 2. PSNR (dB) results of our Baseline with (w) or without (w/o) global self-attention (GSA) branch on the DIV2K validation set.

Extractor	In-scale			Out-of-scale	
	$\times 2$	$\times 3$	$\times 4$	$\times 6$	$\times 12$
w GSA	35.24	31.51	29.50	27.19	24.04
w/o GSA	35.18	31.45	29.45	27.14	24.02

Table 3. PSNR (dB) results of different dimension-reduction operations in global self-attention on DIV2K validation set.

Dimension Reduction	In-scale			Out-of-scale	
	$\times 2$	$\times 3$	$\times 4$	$\times 6$	$\times 12$
Random Matrix	35.22	31.48	29.49	27.16	24.00
Avgpooling	35.23	31.49	29.49	27.18	24.04
Maxpooling	35.24	31.51	29.50	27.19	24.04

2) Importance of the global self-attention (GSA) branch in the MSTB of our feature extraction backbone.

To study this aspect, we conduct experiments by evaluating our ASSR network with or without the GSA branch in each MSTB of our feature extraction backbone. Here, we use the Baseline instead of our TADT to use the complete feature extraction backbone for fully comparison. As shown in Table 2, our ASSR network using the Baseline with GSA achieves a performance gain of 0.06 dB on PSNR over that without GSA, on the DIV2K validation set for $\times 2$ SR. This validates the importance of

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Table 4. PSNR (dB) results of different hyper-parameter settings on Urban100.

Hyper-parameters	In-scale			Out-of-scale	
	$\times 2$	$\times 3$	$\times 4$	$\times 6$	$\times 8$
$\alpha_1 = 0.25, \alpha_2 = 0.25, \alpha_3 = 0.50$	33.65	29.58	27.37	24.75	23.27
$\alpha_1 = 0.00, \alpha_2 = 0.25, \alpha_3 = 1.00$	33.62	29.57	27.37	24.77	23.27
$\alpha_1 = 0.00, \alpha_2 = 0.25, \alpha_3 = 0.50$	33.64	29.52	27.32	24.61	23.02
$\alpha_1 = 0.25, \alpha_2 = 0.50, \alpha_3 = 0.50$	33.64	29.56	27.36	24.74	23.25

GSA branch in our feature extraction backbone for image ASSR.

3) Investigation on dimension reduction in the GSA branch. To this end, we explore other dimension reduction variants, *e.g.*, “Random Matrix” and “Avgpooling” for the GSA branch in our Baseline variant. Here, “Random Matrix” performs dimension reduction by a linear projection matrix of size $m^2 \times d^2$, which is randomly sampled from a normal distribution. For “Avgpooling”, we just replaces the “maxpooling” operation in the GSA by average pooling. As shown in Table 3, the “Maxpooling” employed in GSA achieves slightly better results (0.01~0.04dB) on ASSR tasks at most scales. Thus, we use “Maxpooling” for dimension reduction in the GSA branch.

4) Investigation on the sensitivity of hyper-parameters. We use α_1 , α_2 and α_3 to penalize the predicted β by a loss $\mathcal{L}_\beta = \beta M$, using a binary value $M \triangleq \beta \geq (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 s^{\alpha_3})$ to avoid small β values. α_1 is the lower bound of β to be penalized. α_2 and α_3 should be properly set to adjust the binary value M according to the scale s . We report the experimental results achieved by different hyper-parameter settings on Urban100 in Table 4. We observe that our TADT is not very sensitive to the values of α_1 , α_2 and α_3 once they are properly set, but our setting reported in paper achieves an overall better performance.

3 More Quantitative Results

In Table 5, we provide more quantitative results on Set5, Set14, B100, Urban100, and Manga109.

4 More Visual Comparison on Image ASSR

In Figures 2-7, we provide more visual comparison results of different feature extractors working with three arbitrary-scale upsamplers, *i.e.*, MetaSR [4], LIIF [2], and LTE [6], on the image ASSR task.

Table 5. Quantitative comparison of PSNR (dB) results by different feature extractors working with arbitrary-scale upsamplers on five benchmark datasets. † indicates our implementation, while the others are directly evaluated with the released pre-trained models. The best results are highlighted in **bold**.

Method		Set5			Set14			B100			Urban100			Manga109		
Upsampler	Feature Extractor	×2	×3	×4	×2	×3	×4	×2	×3	×4	×2	×3	×4	×2	×3	×4
MetaSR [4]	RDN [12]	38.22	34.63	32.38	33.98	30.54	28.78	32.33	29.26	27.71	32.92	28.82	26.55	-	-	-
	RCAN† [11]	38.24	34.69	32.44	34.02	30.59	28.81	32.35	29.29	27.73	33.14	28.98	26.66	39.37	34.44	31.26
	NLSA† [8]	38.26	34.76	32.51	34.11	30.68	28.89	32.35	29.30	27.77	33.25	29.12	26.80	39.43	34.55	31.42
	SwinIR [7]	38.26	34.77	32.47	34.14	30.66	28.85	32.39	29.31	27.75	33.29	29.12	26.76	39.42	34.58	31.34
	CAT-R-2† [3]	38.30	34.74	32.40	34.21	30.68	28.83	32.40	29.29	27.72	33.35	29.11	26.69	39.49	34.52	31.17
	Baseline (Ours)	38.29	34.77	32.49	34.11	30.68	28.84	32.40	29.32	27.74	33.34	29.12	26.74	39.47	34.53	31.28
	TADT (Ours)	38.34	34.84	32.58	34.13	30.75	28.92	32.47	29.36	27.80	33.50	29.32	26.96	39.57	34.76	31.59
LIIF [2]	RDN [12]	38.17	34.68	32.50	33.97	30.53	28.80	32.32	29.26	27.74	32.87	28.82	26.68	39.22	34.14	31.15
	RCAN† [11]	38.21	34.74	32.59	34.02	30.61	28.89	32.36	29.29	27.77	33.17	29.03	26.86	39.37	34.34	31.31
	NLSA† [8]	38.30	34.86	32.73	34.22	30.72	28.98	32.39	29.35	27.83	33.44	29.35	27.15	39.58	34.67	31.65
	SwinIR [7]	38.28	34.87	32.73	34.14	30.75	28.98	32.39	29.34	27.84	33.36	29.33	27.15	39.53	34.65	31.67
	CAT-R-2† [3]	38.33	34.91	32.75	34.27	30.79	29.02	32.44	29.38	27.86	33.58	29.44	27.23	39.53	34.66	31.69
	Baseline (Ours)	38.34	34.91	32.78	34.19	30.81	29.03	32.44	29.38	27.85	33.54	29.49	27.27	39.63	34.74	31.77
	TADT (Ours)	38.38	34.96	32.83	34.31	30.83	29.07	32.46	29.41	27.87	33.65	29.58	27.37	39.68	34.79	31.83
LTE [6]	RDN [12]	38.23	34.72	32.61	34.09	30.58	28.88	32.36	29.30	27.77	33.04	28.97	26.81	39.25	34.28	31.27
	RCAN† [11]	38.24	34.77	32.60	34.04	30.64	28.87	32.37	29.31	27.77	33.13	29.04	26.88	39.41	34.39	31.30
	NLSA† [8]	38.35	34.88	32.81	34.28	30.78	29.01	32.43	29.39	27.86	33.56	29.43	27.25	39.64	34.69	31.66
	SwinIR [7]	38.33	34.89	32.81	34.25	30.80	29.06	32.44	29.39	27.86	33.50	29.41	27.24	39.60	34.76	31.76
	CAT-R-2† [3]	38.36	34.91	32.80	34.24	30.81	29.04	32.47	29.39	27.87	33.60	29.48	27.27	39.61	34.75	31.76
	Baseline (Ours)	38.39	34.95	32.84	34.25	30.80	29.06	32.46	29.39	27.86	33.67	29.51	27.33	39.66	34.77	31.77
	TADT (Ours)	38.42	34.99	32.83	34.37	30.84	29.06	32.47	29.41	27.88	33.70	29.57	27.36	39.72	34.86	31.85
ArbSR [9]	ArbSR [9]	38.26	34.76	32.55	34.09	30.64	28.87	32.39	29.32	27.76	33.14	28.98	26.68	39.27	34.55	31.36
	LIRCAN [1]	38.29	34.82	32.68	34.33	30.77	28.97	32.42	29.36	27.82	33.13	29.11	26.88	39.56	34.77	31.71
	EQSR [10]	38.35	34.83	32.71	34.45	30.82	29.12	32.46	29.42	27.86	33.62	29.53	27.30	39.44	34.89	31.86
Upsampler	Feature Extractor	×6	×8	×12	×6	×8	×12	×6	×8	×12	×6	×8	×12	×6	×8	×12
MetaSR [4]	RDN [12]	29.04	26.96	-	26.51	24.97	-	25.90	24.83	-	23.99	22.59	-	-	-	-
	RCAN† [11]	29.02	26.97	24.63	26.55	25.01	23.20	25.91	24.83	23.47	24.06	22.65	21.05	26.97	24.57	22.01
	NLSA† [8]	29.07	27.00	24.72	26.56	25.07	23.25	25.95	24.88	23.51	24.20	22.78	21.15	27.11	24.71	22.13
	SwinIR [7]	29.09	27.02	24.66	26.58	25.09	23.23	25.94	24.87	23.52	24.16	22.75	21.16	26.96	24.62	22.10
	CAT-R-2† [3]	28.98	26.96	24.59	26.52	25.03	23.19	25.91	24.85	23.48	24.11	22.73	21.12	26.86	24.54	22.06
	Baseline (Ours)	29.08	27.01	24.71	26.56	25.07	23.26	25.92	24.85	23.50	24.14	22.74	21.12	26.88	24.53	22.00
	TADT (Ours)	29.16	27.11	24.79	26.65	25.11	23.23	25.97	24.91	23.54	24.32	22.91	21.24	27.20	24.79	22.20
LIIF [2]	RDN [12]	29.15	27.14	24.86	26.64	25.15	23.24	25.98	24.91	23.57	24.20	22.79	21.15	27.30	25.00	22.36
	RCAN† [11]	29.32	27.27	24.81	26.69	25.23	23.29	26.01	24.95	23.59	24.35	22.92	21.24	27.37	25.05	22.39
	NLSA† [8]	29.39	27.24	24.90	26.73	25.26	23.34	26.06	24.99	23.62	24.58	23.07	21.39	27.65	25.26	22.53
	SwinIR [7]	29.46	27.36	24.98	26.82	25.34	23.37	26.07	25.01	23.64	24.59	23.14	21.43	27.66	25.28	22.57
	CAT-R-2† [3]	29.53	27.38	24.98	26.82	25.36	23.37	26.09	25.02	23.62	24.67	23.19	21.47	27.72	25.31	22.58
	Baseline (Ours)	29.45	27.34	25.03	26.80	25.34	23.37	26.08	25.03	23.64	24.68	23.22	21.51	27.74	25.34	22.58
	TADT (Ours)	29.51	27.38	25.01	26.84	25.34	23.38	26.10	25.05	23.65	24.75	23.27	21.53	27.84	25.39	22.59
LTE [6]	RDN [12]	29.32	27.26	24.79	26.71	25.16	23.31	26.01	24.95	23.60	24.28	22.88	21.22	27.46	25.09	22.43
	RCAN† [11]	29.29	27.30	24.91	26.72	25.25	23.34	26.01	24.96	23.62	24.33	22.92	21.29	27.44	25.09	22.43
	NLSA† [8]	29.43	27.33	25.02	26.79	25.32	22.36	26.08	25.02	23.65	24.62	23.15	21.47	27.83	25.37	22.61
	SwinIR [7]	29.50	27.35	25.07	26.86	25.42	23.44	26.09	25.03	23.67	24.62	23.17	21.51	27.81	25.39	22.65
	CAT-R-2† [3]	29.41	27.33	24.96	26.85	25.34	23.40	26.09	25.03	23.65	24.68	23.21	21.50	27.84	25.39	22.66
	Baseline (Ours)	29.46	27.39	25.04	26.86	25.36	23.41	26.09	25.04	23.66	24.67	23.23	21.51	27.85	25.39	22.64
	TADT (Ours)	29.52	27.42	25.10	26.85	25.35	23.44	26.11	25.05	23.67	24.72	23.26	21.54	27.93	25.47	22.70
ArbSR [9]	ArbSR [9]	28.45	26.21	23.69	26.22	24.55	22.55	25.74	24.55	23.07	23.70	22.13	20.40	26.18	23.58	21.05
	EQSR [10]	29.41	-	-	26.79	-	-	26.07	-	-	24.66	-	-	27.97	-	-

Figure 2. Visual comparison of feature extractors integrated with MetaSR [4] on super-resolution natural images at scale 2, 3, 4. The highlighted regions are zoomed in for better view.

Figure 3. Visual comparison of feature extractors integrated with MetaSR [4] on super-resolution natural images at scale 6, 8, 12. The highlighted regions are zoomed in for better view.

Figure 4. Visual comparison of feature extractors integrated with LIIF [2] on super-resolution for natural images at scale 2, 3, 4. The highlighted regions are zoomed in for better view.

Figure 5. Visual comparison of feature extractors integrated with LIIF [2] on super-resolution for natural images at scale 6, 8, 12. The highlighted regions are zoomed in for better view.

Figure 6. Visual comparison of feature extractors integrated with LTE [6] on super-resolution for natural images at scale 2, 3, 4. The highlighted regions are zoomed in for better view.

Figure 7. Visual comparison of feature extractors integrated with LTE [6] on super-resolution for natural images at scale 6, 8, 12. The highlighted regions are zoomed in for better view.

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